

n -Cylindrical Neutrosophic M -open Sets

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Abstract. In this paper, we introduce the concept of an n -cylindrical neutrosophic M -open set, defined as the union of n -cylindrical neutrosophic $\delta\mathcal{P}$ -open sets and n -cylindrical neutrosophic $\theta\mathcal{S}$ -open sets within n -cylindrical neutrosophic topological spaces. We also explore various properties and characterizations of the n -cylindrical neutrosophic M -interior. Furthermore, we apply a suitable measure to a decision-making problem involving the calculation of incentives based on teacher performance during subject instruction.

Keywords: n -CyNM-open sets, n -CyNM-closed sets, n -CyNMint, and n -CyNMcl.

1. Introduction and Preliminaries

Following Zadeh's introduction of fuzzy set (denoted as fs) in 1965 [22], Chang [3] developed the notion of fuzzy topological spaces (fts), which led to the adaptation of classical topological concepts within the framework of fuzzy topology by various researchers. A significant generalization of fuzzy sets, known as intuitionistic fuzzy set (ifs), was introduced by Atanassov in 1986 [2]. Building on this, Coker [4] introduced the concept of intuitionistic fuzzy topological spaces ($ifts$) based on ifs 's. Jeon et al. [7] further investigated intuitionistic fuzzy continuity and pre-continuity within this framework.

With the advent of neutrosophy and neutrosophic sets by Smarandache [15,16], a new direction in uncertainty modeling emerged. Salama and Alblowi [10] introduced neutrosophic crisp set and neutrosophic topological spaces (Nts), extending $ifts$ and incorporating degrees of

membership, indeterminacy, and non-membership for each element. Neutrosophic has formed the foundation for a broader class of theories that generalize both crisp and fuzzy structures.

Smarandache also introduced the concept of dependence degrees between fuzzy and neutrosophic components. Later, Arokiarani et al. [1] introduced the neutrosophic set (NS), wherein the sum of the three membership values does not exceed 3. In the same year, Veereswari [21] proposed the notion of neutrosophic topological spaces (Nts) and studied fundamental operations on them.

Saranya et al. [11] introduced the concept of n -cylindrical neutrosophic set (abbreviated as n - $CyNS$), characterized by α and γ as dependent components and β as an independent component. Apart from neutrosophic set (NS), n - $CyNS$ represents the most extensive generalization of fuzzy sets. In this framework, the membership functions positive (α), neutral (β), & negative (γ) satisfy the conditions $0 \leq \beta_x \leq 1$ & $0 \leq \alpha_x^n(l) + \gamma_x^n(l) \leq 1$, $n > 1$, where $n > 1$ is an integer.

Later, Saranya et al. [12] introduced the notion of n - CyN continuity for functions between two n -cylindrical neutrosophic topological spaces (n - $CyNts$). They also defined the n - CyN interior (n - $CyNint$) and n - CyN closure (n - $CyNcl$) of subsets within n - $CyNts$.

In a related development, El-Maghrabi and Al-Juhani [6] introduced the concept of M -open sets in topological spaces and investigated several of their properties. The class of M -open sets plays a significant role in topological theory due to its applicability across various branches of mathematics and real-world applications. Padma et al. [9] also found M -open sets in nano topological spaces. Vadivel et al. [17–19] discussed some open sets in fuzzy nano and neutrosophic nano topological spaces. Kalaiyarsan et al. [8] and Vadivel et al. [20] introduced M -open sets in fuzzy and neutrosophic nano topological spaces.

Entropy serves as a measure of the degree of uncertainty within a set, regardless of whether the set is fuzzy, intuitionistic, ambiguous, or otherwise imprecise. Given that n - $CyNS$'s are capable of representing uncertain data, it is natural to explore the concept of entropy within the context of n - $CyNS$'s. The first reference to entropy as a measure of fuzziness was made by Zadeh in 1965 [22]. Subsequently, De Luca and Termini [5] provided an axiomatic foundation for a non-probabilistic form of entropy.

The remaining sections of this dissertation are organized as follows: Section 2 provides a brief review of fundamental definitions related to ifs 's, NS 's and n - $CyNS$'s. In Section 3, we introduce the concepts of n - $CyMos$ and n - $CyNMint$ within the framework of n - $CyNts$, and investigate some of their basic properties with illustrative examples. Section 4 presents an entropy measure tailored for n - $CyNS$'s and discusses a real-world application scenario where this measure is effectively utilized. Finally, the conclusions are summarized in Section 5.

Definition 1.1. [12] Let \varkappa & ξ be two n -CyN subsets of an n -CyNts. ξ is called neighbourhood of \varkappa if \exists an n -CyNos, $O \ni \varkappa \subset O \subset \xi$.

Proposition 1.2. [12] $\varkappa \subset X$ is n -CyNos in (X, τ_{CyN}) iff it carries a neighbourhood of its subsets.

Definition 1.3. [12] Let (X, τ_{CyN}) be an n -CyNts and let $\varkappa = \{\langle x, \alpha_\varkappa(x), \beta_\varkappa(x), \gamma_\varkappa(x) \rangle : x \in X\}$ is an n -CyNS in X . Then, the n -cylindrical neutrosophic interior (resp. closure) (briefly, n -CyNint (resp. n -CyNcl)) is defined as (i) n -CyN union of all n -CyN open subsets of X . ie, n -CyNint(\varkappa) = $\bigcup\{G : G \in \tau_{CyN}$ and $G \subseteq \varkappa\}$, (ii) n -CyNcl(\varkappa) = $\bigcap\{K : K \in \tau_{CyNcs}$ and $\varkappa \subseteq K\}$.

Clearly, n -CyNint(\varkappa) is the biggest n -CyNos that is contained by \varkappa , n -CyNcl(\varkappa) is the smallest n -CyNcs that contains \varkappa .

2. n -Cylindrical Neutrosophic M -open sets

In this section, we introduce the concept n -CyNMs & investigate some related properties.

Definition 2.1. Let (X, τ_{CyN}) be an n -CyNts and \varkappa be an n -CyNS. Then,

- (i) \varkappa is called an n -CyN regular open (resp. closed) set (briefly, n -CyNros (resp. n -CyNrcs)), if $\varkappa = n$ -CyNint(n -CyNcl(\varkappa)) (resp. $\varkappa = n$ -CyNcl(n -CyNint(\varkappa))),
- (ii) n -CyN δ int(\varkappa) = $\bigcup\{G|G$ is an n -CyNros & $G \subseteq \varkappa\}$,
- (iii) n -CyN δ cl(\varkappa) = $\bigcap\{K|K$ is an n -CyNrcs & $\varkappa \subseteq K\}$,
- (iv) n -CyN θ int(\varkappa) = $\bigcup\{n$ -CyNint(ξ) : $\xi \subseteq \varkappa$ & ξ is a n -CyNcs in $X\}$,
- (v) n -CyN θ cl(\varkappa) = $\bigcap\{n$ -CyNcl(ξ) : $\varkappa \subseteq \xi$ & ξ is a n -CyNos in $X\}$.

Definition 2.2. Let (X, τ_{CyN}) be an n -CyNts and $\varkappa = \{\langle l, \alpha_\varkappa(l), \beta_\varkappa(l), \gamma_\varkappa(l) \rangle : l \in X\}$ be an n -CyNS in X . A set \varkappa is said to be n -CyN

- (i) δ -open set (briefly, n -CyN δ os), if $\varkappa = n$ -CyN δ int(\varkappa),
- (ii) δ -pre open set (briefly, n -CyN δ Pos), if $\varkappa \subseteq n$ -CyNint(n -CyN δ cl(\varkappa)),
- (iii) δ -semi open set (briefly, n -CyN δ Sos), if $\varkappa \subseteq n$ -CyNcl(n -CyN δ int(\varkappa)),
- (iv) θ -open set (briefly, n -CyN θ os), if $\varkappa = n$ -CyN θ int(\varkappa),
- (v) θ -semi open set (briefly, n -CyN θ Sos), if $\varkappa \subseteq n$ -CyNcl(n -CyN θ int(\varkappa)),
- (vi) e -open set (briefly, n -CyN e os), if $\varkappa = n$ -CyNcl(n -CyN δ int(\varkappa)) \cup n -CyNint(n -CyN δ cl(\varkappa)),
- (vii) M -open set (briefly, n -CyN M os), if $\varkappa \subseteq n$ -CyNcl(n -CyN θ int(\varkappa)) \cup n -CyNint(n -CyN δ cl(\varkappa)).

The complement of a n - $CyNMos$ (resp. n - $CyN\delta os$, n - $CyN\delta Pos$, n - $CyN\delta Sos$, n - $CyN\theta os$, n - $CyN\theta Sos$ & n - $CyNeos$) is called a n - $CyNM$ (resp. n - $CyN\delta$, n - $CyN\delta P$, n - $CyN\delta S$, n - $CyN\theta$, n - $CyN\theta S$ & n - $CyNe$) closed set (briefly, n - $CyNMcs$ (resp. n - $CyN\delta cs$, n - $CyN\delta Pcs$, n - $CyN\delta Scs$, n - $CyN\theta cs$, n - $CyN\theta Scs$ & n - $CyNecs$)) in X .

The family of all n - $CyNMos$ (resp. n - $CyNMcs$, n - $CyN\delta os$, n - $CyN\delta cs$, n - $CyN\delta Pos$, n - $CyN\delta Pcs$, n - $CyN\delta Sos$, n - $CyN\delta Scs$, n - $CyN\theta os$, n - $CyN\theta cs$, n - $CyN\theta Sos$, n - $CyN\theta Scs$, n - $CyNeos$ & n - $CyNecs$) of X is denoted by n - $CyNMOS(X)$, (resp. n - $CyNMCS(X)$, n - $CyN\delta OS(X)$, n - $CyN\delta CS(X)$, n - $CyN\delta POS(X)$, n - $CyN\delta PCS(X)$, n - $CyN\delta SOS(X)$, n - $CyN\delta SCS(X)$, n - $CyN\theta OS(X)$, n - $CyN\theta CS(X)$, n - $CyN\theta SOS(X)$, n - $CyN\theta SCS(X)$, n - $CyNeOS(X)$ & n - $CyNeCS(X)$).

Definition 2.3. Let (X, τ_{CyN}) be an n - $CyNts$ and $\varkappa = \{\langle l, \alpha_\varkappa(l), \beta_\varkappa(l), \gamma_\varkappa(l) \rangle : l \in X\}$ be an n - $CyNS$ in X . Then, the n - CyN

- (i) M -interior (resp. n - $CyN\delta$ -interior, n - $CyN\delta P$ -interior, n - $CyN\delta S$ -interior, n - $CyN\theta$ -interior, n - $CyN\theta S$ -interior & n - $CyNe$ -interior) of \varkappa (briefly, n - $CyNMint(\varkappa)$ (resp. n - $CyN\delta int(\varkappa)$, n - $CyN\delta Pint(\varkappa)$, n - $CyN\delta Sint(\varkappa)$, n - $CyN\theta int(\varkappa)$, n - $CyN\theta Sint(\varkappa)$ & n - $CyNeint(\varkappa)$) is defined by n - $CyNMint(\varkappa)$ (resp. n - $CyN\delta int(\varkappa)$, n - $CyN\delta Pint(\varkappa)$, n - $CyN\delta Sint(\varkappa)$, n - $CyN\theta int(\varkappa)$, n - $CyN\theta Sint(\varkappa)$ & n - $CyNeint(\varkappa)$) = $\bigcup\{G : G \subseteq \varkappa$ and G is a n - $CyNMos$ (resp. n - $CyN\delta os$, n - $CyN\delta Pos$, n - $CyN\delta Sos$, n - $CyN\theta os$, n - $CyN\theta Sos$ & n - $CyNeos$) in $X\}$.
- (ii) M -closure (resp. n - $CyN\delta$ -closure, n - $CyN\delta PP$ -closure, n - $CyN\delta S$ -closure, n - $CyN\theta$ -closure, n - $CyN\theta S$ -closure & n - $CyNe$ -closure) of \varkappa (briefly, n - $CyNMcl(\varkappa)$ (resp. n - $CyN\delta cl(\varkappa)$, n - $CyN\delta Pcl(\varkappa)$, n - $CyN\delta Scl(\varkappa)$, n - $CyN\theta cl(\varkappa)$, n - $CyN\theta Scl(\varkappa)$ & n - $CyNecl(\varkappa)$) is defined by n - $CyNMcl(\varkappa)$ (resp. n - $CyN\delta cl(\varkappa)$, n - $CyN\delta Pcl(\varkappa)$, n - $CyN\delta Scl(\varkappa)$, n - $CyN\theta cl(\varkappa)$, n - $CyN\theta Scl(\varkappa)$ & n - $CyNecl(\varkappa)$) = $\bigcap\{K : \varkappa \subseteq K$ and K is a n - $CyNMcs$ (resp. n - $CyN\delta cs$, n - $CyN\delta Pcs$, n - $CyN\delta Scs$, n - $CyN\theta cs$, n - $CyN\theta Scs$ & n - $CyNecs$) in $X\}$.

Proposition 2.4. Let (X, τ_{CyN}) be a n - $CyNts$. Then, every

- (i) n - $CyN\theta os$ (resp. n - $CyN\theta cs$) is a n - $CyNos$ (resp. n - $CyNcs$),
- (ii) n - $CyN\theta os$ (resp. n - $CyN\theta cs$) is a n - $CyN\theta Sos$ (resp. n - $CyN\theta Scs$),
- (iii) n - $CyN\theta Sos$ (resp. n - $CyN\theta Scs$) is a n - $CyNMos$ (resp. n - $CyNMcs$),
- (iv) n - $CyN\delta os$ (resp. n - $CyN\delta cs$) is a n - $CyNos$ (resp. n - $CyNcs$),
- (v) n - $CyN\delta os$ (resp. n - $CyN\delta cs$) is a n - $CyN\delta Pos$ (resp. n - $CyN\delta Pcs$),
- (vi) n - $CyN\delta os$ (resp. n - $CyN\delta cs$) is a n - $CyN\delta Sos$ (resp. n - $CyN\delta Scs$),
- (vii) n - $CyN\delta Sos$ (resp. n - $CyN\delta Scs$) is a n - $CyNeos$ (resp. n - $CyNecs$),
- (viii) n - $CyN\delta Pos$ (resp. n - $CyN\delta Pcs$) is a n - $CyNMos$ (resp. n - $CyNMcs$),

(ix) n -CyNMOs (resp. n -CyNMCs) is a n -CyNeos (resp. n -CyNecs).

Proof.

- (i) If S is a n -CyN θ os in U , then $S = n$ -CyN θ int(S) \subseteq n -CyNint(S). Therefore, S is a n -CyNos.
- (ii) If S is a n -CyN θ os in U , then $S = n$ -CyN θ int(S). So, $S = n$ -CyN θ int(S) \subseteq n -CyNcl(n -CyN θ int(S)). Therefore, S is a n -CyN θ Sos.
- (iii) If S is a n -CyN θ Sos in U , then $S \subseteq n$ -CyNcl(n -CyN θ int(S)). So, $S \subseteq n$ -CyNcl(n -CyN θ int(S)) \subseteq n -CyNcl(n -CyN θ int(S)) \cup n -CyNint(n -CyN δ cl(S)). Therefore, S is a n -CyNMOs.
- (iv) If S is a n -CyN δ os in U , then $S = n$ -CyN δ int(S) \subseteq n -CyNint(S). Therefore, S is a n -CyNos.
- (v) If S is a n -CyN δ os in U , then $S = n$ -CyN δ int(S). So, $S = n$ -CyN δ int(S) \subseteq n -CyNint(S) \subseteq n -CyNint(n -CyN δ cl(S)). Therefore, S is a n -CyN δ Pos.
- (vi) If S is a n -CyN δ os in U , then $S = n$ -CyN δ int(S). So, $S = n$ -CyN δ int(S) \subseteq n -CyNcl(n -CyN δ int(S)). Therefore, S is a n -CyN δ Sos.
- (vii) If S is a n -CyN δ Sos in U , then $S \subseteq n$ -CyNcl(n -CyN δ int(S)) \subseteq n -CyNcl((n -CyN δ int(S)) \cup n -CyNint(n -CyN δ cl(S))). Therefore, S is a n -CyNeos.
- (viii) If S is a n -CyN δ Pos in U , then $S \subseteq n$ -CyNint(n -CyN δ cl(S)) \subseteq n -CyNcl(n -CyN θ int(S)) \cup n -CyNint(n -CyN δ cl(S)). Therefore, S is a n -CyNMOs.
- (ix) If S is a n -CyNMOs then $S \subseteq n$ -CyNcl(n -CyN θ int(S)) \cup n -CyNint(n -CyN δ cl(S)). So, $S \subseteq n$ -CyNcl(n -CyN θ int(S)) \cup n -CyNint(n -CyN δ cl(S)) \subseteq n -CyNint(n -CyN δ cl(S)) \subseteq n -CyNcl(n -CyN δ int(S)) \cup n -CyNint(n -CyN δ cl(S))). Therefore S is a n -CyNeos. It is also true for their respective closed sets.

□

Example 2.5. Let $X = \{x_1, x_2\}$ and the n -cylindrical neutrosophic sets $\varkappa_1, \varkappa_2, \varkappa_3, \varkappa_4, \varkappa_5, \varkappa_6, \varkappa_7$ in X are defined as

$$\varkappa_1 = \{\langle x_1, 0.1250732, 0.50, 0.1850738 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.1450734, 0.50, 0.1650736 \rangle\}$$

$$\varkappa_2 = \{\langle x_1, 0.1150731, 0.50, 0.1950739 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.1350733, 0.50, 0.1750737 \rangle\}$$

$$\varkappa_3 = \{\langle x_1, 0.1950739, 0.50, 0.1150731 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.1750737, 0.50, 0.1350733 \rangle\}$$

$$\varkappa_4 = \{\langle x_1, 0.1250732, 0.50, 0.1850738 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.1350733, 0.50, 0.1750737 \rangle\}$$

$$\varkappa_5 = \{\langle x_1, 0.1250732, 0.50, 0.1850738 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.1350733, 0.50, 0.1650736 \rangle\}$$

$$\varkappa_6 = \{\langle x_1, 0.1450734, 0.50, 0.1250732 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.1450734, 0.50, 0.1450734 \rangle\}$$

$$\varkappa_7 = \{\langle x_1, 0.1850738, 0.50, 0.1250732 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.1650736, 0.50, 0.1450734 \rangle\}$$

Then, we have $\tau_{CyN} = \{0_{CyN}, 1_{CyN}, \varkappa_1, \varkappa_2, \varkappa_3, \varkappa_4\}$ be a $n-CyNt$ on X . Then,

- (i) \varkappa_1 is a $n-CyNos$ (resp. $n-CyFMos$) but not $n-CyN\theta os$ (resp. $n-CyN\theta S os$)
- (ii) \varkappa_7 is a $n-CyN\theta S os$ (resp. $n-CyN\delta S os, n-CyNMos$) but not $n-CyN\theta os$ (resp. $n-CyN\delta os, n-CyN\delta P os$)
- (iii) \varkappa_4 is a $n-CyNos$ (resp. $n-CyN\delta P os, n-CyN eos$) but not $n-CyN\delta os$ (resp. $n-CyN\delta os, n-CyN\delta S os$)
- (iv) \varkappa_6 is a $n-CyN eos$ but not $n-CyNMos$

Remark 2.6. The diagram shows that $n-CyNMos$'s in $n-CyNts$.

Diagram 2.7. From the above Proposition 2.4, and the Example 2.5, the following implications are hold.

Theorem 2.8. The statements are true.

- (i) $n-CyN\theta Scl(\varkappa) = \varkappa \cup n-CyNint(n-CyN\theta cl(\varkappa))$
- (ii) $n-CyN\theta Sint(\varkappa) = \varkappa \cap n-CyNcl(n-CyN\theta int(\varkappa))$
- (iii) $n-CyN\delta Pcl(\varkappa) = \varkappa \cup n-CyNcl(n-CyN\delta int(\varkappa))$
- (iv) $n-CyN\delta Pint(\varkappa) = \varkappa \cap n-CyNint(n-CyN\delta cl(\varkappa))$
- (v) $n-CyN\delta Pcl(n-CyN\delta Pint(\varkappa)) = n-CyN\delta Pint(\varkappa) \cup n-CyNcl(n-CyN\delta int(\varkappa))$
- (vi) $n-CyN\delta Pint(n-CyN\delta Pcl(\varkappa)) = n-CyN\delta Pcl(\varkappa) \cap n-CyNint(n-CyN\delta cl(\varkappa))$
- (vii) $n-CyN\delta Sint(\varkappa) = \varkappa \cap n-CyNcl(n-CyN\delta int(\varkappa))$
- (viii) $n-CyN\delta Scl(\varkappa) = \varkappa \cup n-CyNint(n-CyN\delta cl(\varkappa))$
- (ix) $n-CyN\delta int(\varkappa) = n-CyN\delta cl(n-CyN\delta int(\varkappa))$
- (x) $n-CyNint(n-CyN\delta cl(\varkappa)) = n-CyN\delta int(n-CyN\delta cl(\varkappa))$

Theorem 2.9. Let (X, τ_{CyN}) be a $n-CyNts$. Let \varkappa be any $n-CyN$ subset in X . Then,

- (i) $n-CyNMcl(1_{CyN} - \varkappa) = 1_{CyN} - n-CyNMint(\varkappa)$ (or) $n-CyNMcl(\varkappa^c) = (n-CyNMint(\varkappa))^c$

(ii) $n\text{-CyNMint}(1_{CyN} - \varkappa) = 1_{CyN} - n\text{-CyNMcl}(\varkappa)$ (or) $n\text{-CyNM}(\varkappa^c) = (n\text{-CyNMcl}(\varkappa))^c$

Remark 2.10. Taking complements on either side of (i) & (ii) of Theorem 2.9, we get $n\text{-CyNMint}(\varkappa) = 1_{CyN} - n\text{-CyNMcl}(1_{CyN} - \varkappa)$ and $n\text{-CyNMcl}(\varkappa) = 1_{CyN} - n\text{-CyNMint}(1_{CyN} - \varkappa)$.

Theorem 2.11. Let (X, τ_{CyN}) be a $n\text{-CyNts}$ and $\varkappa \subseteq X$. Then, \varkappa is a $n\text{-CyNMos}$ iff $\varkappa = n\text{-CyN}\theta\mathcal{Sint}(\varkappa) \cup n\text{-CyN}\delta\mathcal{Pint}(\varkappa)$.

Proof. Let \varkappa be a $n\text{-CyNMos}$. Then, $\varkappa \subseteq n\text{-CyNcl}(n\text{-CyN}\theta\mathcal{int}(\varkappa)) \cup n\text{-CyNint}(n\text{-CyN}\delta\mathcal{cl}(\varkappa))$. By Theorem 2.8, we have

$$\begin{aligned} n\text{-CyN}\delta\mathcal{Pint}(\varkappa) \cup n\text{-CyN}\theta\mathcal{Sint}(\varkappa) &= (\varkappa \cap (n\text{-CyNcl}(n\text{-CyN}\theta\mathcal{int}(\varkappa)))) \cup (\varkappa \cap (n\text{-CyNint}(n\text{-CyN}\delta\mathcal{cl}(\varkappa)))) \\ &= \varkappa \cap n\text{-CyNcl}(n\text{-CyN}\theta\mathcal{int}(\varkappa)) \cup (n\text{-CyNint}(n\text{-CyN}\delta\mathcal{cl}(\varkappa))) \\ &= \varkappa \end{aligned}$$

Conversely, if $\varkappa = n\text{-CyN}\theta\mathcal{Sint}(\varkappa) \cup n\text{-CyN}\delta\mathcal{Pint}(\varkappa)$ then, Theorem 2.8,

$$\begin{aligned} \varkappa &= n\text{-CyN}\theta\mathcal{Sint}(\varkappa) \cup n\text{-CyN}\delta\mathcal{Pint}(\varkappa) \\ &= (\varkappa \cap n\text{-CyNcl}(n\text{-CyN}\theta\mathcal{int}(\varkappa))) \cup (\varkappa \cap n\text{-CyNint}(n\text{-CyN}\delta\mathcal{cl}(\varkappa))) \\ &= \varkappa \cap (n\text{-CyNcl}(n\text{-CyN}\theta\mathcal{int}(\varkappa)) \cup n\text{-CyNint}(n\text{-CyN}\delta\mathcal{cl}(\varkappa))) \\ &\subseteq n\text{-CyNcl}(n\text{-CyN}\theta\mathcal{int}(\varkappa)) \cup n\text{-CyNint}(n\text{-CyN}\delta\mathcal{cl}(\varkappa)) \end{aligned}$$

and hence, \varkappa is a $n\text{-CyNMos}$.

Theorem 2.12. Let (X, τ_{CyN}) be a $n\text{-CyNts}$ and $\varkappa \subseteq X$. Then, \varkappa is a $n\text{-CyNMcs}$ iff $\varkappa = n\text{-CyN}\theta\mathcal{Scl}(\varkappa) \cap n\text{-CyN}\delta\mathcal{Pcl}(\varkappa)$.

Proof. From Theorem 2.11, it follows. □

Theorem 2.13. The union (resp. intersection) of any family of $n\text{-CyNMOS}(X)$ (resp. $n\text{-CyNMCS}(X)$) is a $n\text{-CyNMOS}(X)$ (resp. $n\text{-CyNMCS}(X)$).

Remark 2.14. The intersection of two $n\text{-CyNMos}$'s need not be $n\text{-CyNMos}$.

Example

2.15.

Let $X = \{x_1, x_2\}$ and the n -cylindrical neutrosophic sets $\varkappa_1, \varkappa_2, \varkappa_3, \varkappa_4, \varkappa_5, \varkappa_6, \varkappa_7$ in X are

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defined as

$$\begin{aligned}\varkappa_1 &= \{\langle x_1, 0.1250732, 0.50, 0.1850738 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.1450734, 0.50, 0.1650736 \rangle\} \\ \varkappa_2 &= \{\langle x_1, 0.1150731, 0.50, 0.1950739 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.1350733, 0.50, 0.1750737 \rangle\} \\ \varkappa_3 &= \{\langle x_1, 0.1950739, 0.50, 0.1150731 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.1750737, 0.50, 0.1350733 \rangle\} \\ \varkappa_4 &= \{\langle x_1, 0.1250732, 0.50, 0.1850738 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.1350733, 0.50, 0.1750737 \rangle\} \\ \varkappa_5 &= \{\langle x_1, 0.1750737, 0.50, 0.1650736 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.1450734, 0.50, 0.1050730 \rangle\} \\ \varkappa_6 &= \{\langle x_1, 0.1550735, 0.50, 0.1050730 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.1950739, 0.50, 0.1750737 \rangle\} \\ \varkappa_7 &= \{\langle x_1, 0.1550735, 0.50, 0.1650736 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.1450734, 0.50, 0.1750737 \rangle\}\end{aligned}$$

Let $\tau_{CyN} = \{0_{CyN}, 1_{CyN}, \varkappa_1, \varkappa_2, \varkappa_3, \varkappa_4\}$ be a $nCyNt$ on X , then \varkappa_5 and \varkappa_6 are $n-CyNMos$ but not $\varkappa_5 \cap \varkappa_6 = \varkappa_7$ is not $n-CyNMos$.

Proposition 2.16. Let (X, τ_{CyN}) be a $n-CyNts$. If \varkappa is a

- (i) $n-CyNMos$ and $n-CyN\theta int(\varkappa) = 0_{CyN}$, then \varkappa is a $n-CyN\delta\mathcal{P}os$,
- (ii) $n-CyNMos$ and $n-CyN\delta cl(\varkappa) = 0_{CyN}$, then \varkappa is a $n-CyN\theta\mathcal{S}os$,
- (iii) $n-CyNMos$ and $n-CyN\delta cs$, then \varkappa is a $n-CyN\theta\mathcal{S}os$,
- (iv) $n-CyN\theta\mathcal{S}os$ and $n-CyN\delta cs$, then \varkappa is a $n-CyNMos$.

Theorem 2.17. \varkappa is a $n-CyNMcs$ (resp. $n-CyNMos$), iff $\varkappa = n-CyNMcl(\varkappa)$ (resp. $\varkappa = n-CyNMint(\varkappa)$).

Proof. Suppose $\varkappa = n-CyNMcl(\varkappa) = \cap\{\xi : \varkappa \subseteq \xi \ \& \ \xi \text{ is a } n-CyNMcs\}$. This means $\varkappa \in \cap\{\xi : \varkappa \subseteq \xi \ \& \ \xi \text{ is a } n-CyNMcs\}$ and hence \varkappa is $n-CyNMcs$. Conversely, suppose \varkappa be a $n-CyNMcs$ in X . Then, we have $\varkappa \in \cap\{\xi : \varkappa \subseteq \xi \ \& \ \xi \text{ is a } n-CyNMcs\}$. Hence, $\varkappa \subseteq \xi$ implies $\varkappa = \cap\{\xi : \varkappa \subseteq \xi \ \& \ \xi \text{ is a } n-CyNMcs\} = n-CyNMcl(\varkappa)$. Similarly $\varkappa = n-CyNMint(\varkappa)$. \square

Theorem 2.18. Let (X, τ_{CyN}) be a $n-CyNts$. Let \varkappa & ξ in X , then the $n-CyNMint$ we have

- (i) $n-CyNMint(0_{CyN}) = 0_{CyN}, n-CyNMint(1_{CyN}) = 1_{CyN}$,
- (ii) $n-CyNMint(\varkappa)$ is a $n-CyNMos$ in X ,
- (iii) $n-CyNMint(\varkappa) \subseteq n-CyNMint(\xi)$ if $\varkappa \subseteq \xi$,
- (iv) $n-CyNMint(n-CyNMint(\varkappa)) = n-CyNMint(\varkappa)$.

Theorem 2.19. Let (X, τ_{CyN}) be a $n-CyNts$. Let \varkappa & ξ in X , then the $n-CyNMcl$ we have,

- (i) $n-CyNMcl(0_{CyN}) = 0_{CyN}, n-CyNMcl(1_{CyN}) = 1_{CyN}$,
- (ii) $n-CyNMcl(\varkappa)$ is a $n-CyNMcs$ in X ,
- (iii) $n-CyNMcl(\varkappa) \subseteq n-CyNMcl(\xi)$ if $\varkappa \subseteq \xi$,
- (iv) $n-CyNMcl(n-CyNMcl(\varkappa)) = n-CyNMcl(\varkappa)$.

Proposition 2.20. Let (X, τ_{CyN}) be a n - $CyNts$. Let \varkappa and ξ are n - CyN subsets in X , then

- (i) n - $CyNMcl(\varkappa^c) = [n$ - $CyNMint(\varkappa)]^c, n$ - $CyNMint(\varkappa^c) = [n$ - $CyNMcl(\varkappa)]^c,$
- (ii) n - $CyNMcl(\varkappa \cup \xi) \supseteq n$ - $CyNMcl(\varkappa) \cup n$ - $CyNMcl(\xi), n$ - $CyNMcl(\varkappa \cap \xi) \subseteq n$ - $CyNMcl(\varkappa) \cap n$ - $CyNMcl(\xi),$
- (iii) n - $CyNMint(\varkappa \cup \xi) \supseteq n$ - $CyNMint(\varkappa) \cup n$ - $CyNMint(\xi), n$ - $CyNMint(\varkappa \cap \xi) \subseteq n$ - $CyNMint(\varkappa) \cap n$ - $CyNMint(\xi).$

Proposition 2.21. Let (X, τ_{CyN}) be a n - $CyNts$. If \varkappa is a n - $CyNS$ in X , then

- (i) n - $CyNMcl(\varkappa) \supseteq n$ - $CyNcl(n$ - $CyN\delta int(\varkappa)) \cap n$ - $CyNint(n$ - $CyN\theta cl(\varkappa)),$
- (ii) n - $CyNMint(\varkappa) \subseteq n$ - $CyNcl(n$ - $CyN\theta int(\varkappa)) \cup n$ - $CyNint(\delta cl(\varkappa)).$

Theorem 2.22. Let (X, τ_{CyN}) be a n - $CyNts$. Let \varkappa be a n - $CyNS$ in X , then

- (i) n - $CyNMcl(\varkappa) = n$ - $CyN\delta Pcl(\varkappa) \cap n$ - $CyN\theta Scl(\varkappa),$
- (ii) n - $CyNMint(\varkappa) = n$ - $CyN\delta Pint(\varkappa) \cup n$ - $CyN\theta Sint(\varkappa).$

Proof.

- (i) It is obvious that, n - $CyNMcl(\varkappa) \subseteq n$ - $CyN\delta Pcl(\varkappa) \cap n$ - $CyN\theta Scl(\varkappa)$. Conversely, from Definition 2.1, we have

$$\begin{aligned} n\text{-}CyNMcl(\varkappa) &\supseteq n\text{-}CyNcl(n\text{-}CyN\delta int(n\text{-}CyNMcl(\varkappa))) \cap n\text{-}CyNint(n\text{-}CyN\theta cl(n\text{-}CyNMcl(\varkappa))) \\ &\supseteq n\text{-}CyNcl(n\text{-}CyN\delta int(\varkappa)) \cap n\text{-}CyNint(n\text{-}CyN\theta cl(\varkappa)) \end{aligned}$$

Since, n - $CyNMcl(\varkappa)$ is n - $CyNMcs$, By Theorem 2.8, we have

$$\begin{aligned} n\text{-}CyN\delta Pcl(\varkappa) \cap n\text{-}CyN\theta Scl(\varkappa) &= (\varkappa \cup n\text{-}CyNcl(n\text{-}CyN\delta int(\varkappa))) \cap (\varkappa \cup n\text{-}CyNint(n\text{-}CyN\theta cl(\varkappa))) \\ &= \varkappa \cap (n\text{-}CyNcl(n\text{-}CyN\delta int(\varkappa)) \cap n\text{-}CyNint(n\text{-}CyN\theta cl(\varkappa))) \\ &= \varkappa \subseteq n\text{-}CyNMcl(\varkappa) \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, n - $CyNMcl(\varkappa) = n$ - $CyN\delta Pcl(\varkappa) \cap n$ - $CyN\theta Scl(\varkappa)$.

- (ii) It follows from (i).

Lemma 2.23. Let (X, τ_{CyN}) be n - $CyNts$ on X and \varkappa be an n - $CyNS$ on X . Then,

- (i) n - $CyNPint(n$ - $CyN\delta Pcl(\varkappa)) = n$ - $CyN\delta Pcl(\varkappa) \cap n$ - $CyNint(n$ - $CyNcl(\varkappa))$ and n - $CyNPcl(n$ - $CyN\delta Pint(\varkappa)) = n$ - $CyN\delta Pint(\varkappa) \cup n$ - $CyNcl(n$ - $CyNint(\varkappa))$
- (ii) n - $CyN\theta Pint(n$ - $CyN\delta Pcl(\varkappa)) = n$ - $CyN\delta Pcl(\varkappa) \cap n$ - $CyNint(n$ - $CyN\theta cl(\varkappa))$ and n - $CyN\theta Pcl(n$ - $CyN\delta Pint(\varkappa)) = n$ - $CyN\delta Pint(\varkappa) \cup n$ - $CyNcl(n$ - $CyN\theta int(\varkappa))$
- (iii) n - $CyN\theta Scl(n$ - $CyN\theta int(\varkappa)) = n$ - $CyNScl(n$ - $CyN\theta int(\varkappa)) = n$ - $CyNint(n$ - $CyNcl(n$ - $CyN\theta int(\varkappa)))$

Proof. Obvious.

Proposition 2.24. Let \varkappa be a n -CyN subsets of a n -CyNts of (X, τ_{CyN}) . Then,

- (i) n -CyNMcl(\varkappa) = $\varkappa \cup n$ -CyN θ Pint(n -CyN δ Pcl(\varkappa))
- (ii) n -CyNMint(\varkappa) = $\varkappa \cap n$ -CyN θ Pcl(n -CyN δ Pint(\varkappa))

Proof.

- (i) By Lemma 2.23,

$$\begin{aligned} \varkappa \cup n\text{-CyN}\theta\text{Pint}(n\text{-CyN}\delta\text{Pcl}(\varkappa)) &= \varkappa \cup (n\text{-CyN}\delta\text{Pcl}(\varkappa) \cap n\text{-CyNint}(n\text{-CyN}\theta\text{cl}(\varkappa))) \\ &= \varkappa \cup (n\text{-CyN}\delta\text{Pcl}(\varkappa)) \cap (\varkappa \cup n\text{-CyNint}(n\text{-CyN}\theta\text{cl}(\varkappa))) \\ &= n\text{-CyN}\delta\text{Pcl}(\varkappa) \cap n\text{-CyN}\theta\text{Scl}(\varkappa) \\ &= n\text{-CyNMcl}(\varkappa) \end{aligned}$$

- (ii) It follows from (i).

Theorem 2.25. Let (X, τ_{CyN}) be a n -CyNts. Let \varkappa be in X , then

- (i) \varkappa is an n -CyNMos
- (ii) $\varkappa \subseteq n$ -CyN θ Pcl(n -CyN δ Pint(\varkappa))
- (iii) n -CyN θ Pcl(\varkappa) = n -CyN θ Pcl(n -CyN δ Pint(\varkappa)) are equivalent.

Proof.

(i) \rightarrow (ii): Let \varkappa be an n -CyNMos. Then by Theorem 2.18, $\varkappa = n$ -CyNMint(\varkappa) and by Proposition 2.24, $\varkappa = \varkappa \cap n$ -CyN θ Pcl(n -CyN δ Pint(\varkappa)) and hence, $\varkappa \subseteq n$ -CyN θ Pcl(n -CyN δ Pint(\varkappa)).

(ii) \rightarrow (i): Let $\varkappa \subseteq n$ -CyN θ Pcl(n -CyN δ Pint(\varkappa)). Then by Proposition 2.21, $\varkappa \subseteq \varkappa \cap n$ -CyN θ Pcl(n -CyN δ Pint(\varkappa)) = n -CyNMint(\varkappa). So, $\varkappa \subseteq n$ -CyNMint(\varkappa) and hence, \varkappa is an n -CyNMos.

(ii) \rightarrow (iii): Let $\varkappa \subseteq n$ -CyN θ Pcl(n -CyN δ Pint(\varkappa)). Then n -CyN θ Pcl(\varkappa) $\subseteq n$ -CyN θ Pcl(n -CyN δ Pint(\varkappa)) and hence, n -CyN θ Pcl(\varkappa) = n -CyN θ Pcl(n -CyN δ Pint(\varkappa)).

- (iii) \rightarrow (ii): Obvious.

Theorem 2.26. Let (X, τ_{CyN}) be a n -CyNts. Let \varkappa be in X , then the following are equivalent.

- (i) \varkappa is an n -CyNMcs
- (ii) n -CyN θ Pint(n -CyN δ Pcl(\varkappa)) $\subseteq \varkappa$
- (iii) n -CyN θ Pint(\varkappa) = n -CyN θ Pint(n -CyN δ Pcl(\varkappa))

Proof. From Theorem 2.25, it follows.

3. Application

Zadeh was the first to propose entropy as a fuzziness measures [22]. Several entropy measures were later defined by numerous mathematicians. The definition of an entropy measure for n - $CyNS$'s that links the degree of positive, negative, and neutral membership is the main goal of this section. We have used the suggested entropy measure, for instance, in the evaluation criteria of jury selection.

Definition 3.1. [14] Let $\varkappa = \{\langle \alpha_\varkappa, \beta_\varkappa, \gamma_\varkappa \rangle\}$ be an n - $CyNS$ in X . The new entropy measure for \varkappa denoted by n - $CyNE_{npy}(\varkappa)$, is a function, n - $CyNE_{npy} : \tau_N(X) \rightarrow [0, 1]$ and is defined as

$$n\text{-}CyNE_{npy}(\varkappa) = 1 - \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (\alpha_\varkappa - \gamma_\varkappa)^2 (1 - \beta_\varkappa) ; \text{ for every } x_i \in \varkappa$$

Example 3.2. In order to ensure transparent jury selection, five jurors were selected from the pool, given five of their verdicts to review, asked to evaluate the cases during the voir dire, and asked to complete the rubrics. The tables indicate that n - CyN linguistic terms were employed in the jurors' evaluations. To choose the best juror in voir dire, we use the n - CyN entropy metric.

Table 4.1: Linguistic terms

Linguistic Terms	$\langle \alpha, \beta, \gamma \rangle$
Observe (♠)	$\langle 0.1950739, 0.70, 0.1150731 \rangle$
Query (♥)	$\langle 0.1850738, 0.60, 0.1150731 \rangle$
Advocate for clarification (♣)	$\langle 0.1750737, 0.50, 0.1250732 \rangle$
Suggest refinement (◇)	$\langle 0.1650736, 0.50, 0.1250732 \rangle$
Take exception to(♠)	$\langle 0.1550735, 0.50, 0.1550735 \rangle$
Decry (*)	$\langle 0.1450734, 0.40, 0.1650736 \rangle$
Repudiate (●)	$\langle 0.1250732, 0.30, 0.1750737 \rangle$
Excoriate (↓)	$\langle 0.1150731, 0.20, 0.1950739 \rangle$

Juror - 1:

Table 4.2: criticism made by juror - 1

cases \ juries	jury - 1	jury - 2	jury - 3
	1	♥	♥
2	♣	♣	♣
3	♠	♠	♠
4	♠	♠	♠
5	♠	♠	*

Juror - 2:

Table 4.3: criticism made by juror - 2

cases \ juries	jury - 1	jury - 2	jury - 3
	1	♣	♣
2	◇	♣	◇
3	◇	◇	♠
4	♠	♣	♣
5	*	♠	*

Juror - 3:

Table 4.4: criticism made by juror - 3

cases \ juries	jury - 1	jury - 2	jury - 3
1	♥	♣	♣
2	♣	♣	♣
3	◇	♠	◇
4	♠	♠	♠
5	*	♠	*

Juror - 4:

Table 4.5: criticism made by juror - 4

cases \ juries	jury - 1	jury - 2	jury - 3
1	•	↓	♠
2	♥	↓	♠
3	*	♣	•
4	◇	♠	♠
5	♣	♠	◇

Juror - 5:

Table 4.6: criticism made by juror - 5

cases \ juries	jury - 1	jury - 2	jury - 3
1	♠	♥	♣
2	↓	•	*
3	♥	♣	◇
4	•	♠	◇
5	♣	◇	♠

Juror - 1:

Table 4.7: *n-CyN* values of criticism made by juror- 1

cases \ juries	jury - 1	jury - 2	jury - 3
1	$\langle 0.1850738, 0.60, 0.1150731 \rangle$	$\langle 0.1850738, 0.60, 0.1150731 \rangle$	$\langle 0.1950739, 0.70, 0.1150731 \rangle$
2	$\langle 0.1750737, 0.50, 0.1250732 \rangle$	$\langle 0.1750737, 0.50, 0.1250732 \rangle$	$\langle 0.1750737, 0.50, 0.1250732 \rangle$
3	$\langle 0.1550735, 0.50, 0.1550735 \rangle$	$\langle 0.1550735, 0.50, 0.1550735 \rangle$	$\langle 0.1550735, 0.50, 0.1550735 \rangle$
4	$\langle 0.1950739, 0.70, 0.1150731 \rangle$	$\langle 0.1950739, 0.70, 0.1150731 \rangle$	$\langle 0.1950739, 0.70, 0.1150731 \rangle$
5	$\langle 0.1550735, 0.50, 0.1550735 \rangle$	$\langle 0.1550735, 0.50, 0.1550735 \rangle$	$\langle 0.1450734, 0.40, 0.1650736 \rangle$

Juror - 2:

Table 4.8: *n-CyN* values of criticism made by juror - 2

cases \ juries	jury - 1	jury - 2	jury - 3
1	$\langle 0.1750737, 0.50, 0.1250732 \rangle$	$\langle 0.1750737, 0.50, 0.1250732 \rangle$	$\langle 0.1750737, 0.50, 0.1250732 \rangle$
2	$\langle 0.1650736, 0.50, 0.1250732 \rangle$	$\langle 0.1750737, 0.50, 0.1250732 \rangle$	$\langle 0.1650736, 0.50, 0.1250732 \rangle$
3	$\langle 0.1650736, 0.50, 0.1250732 \rangle$	$\langle 0.1650736, 0.50, 0.1250732 \rangle$	$\langle 0.1550735, 0.50, 0.1550735 \rangle$
4	$\langle 0.1950739, 0.70, 0.1150731 \rangle$	$\langle 0.1750737, 0.50, 0.1250732 \rangle$	$\langle 0.1750737, 0.50, 0.1250732 \rangle$
5	$\langle 0.1450734, 0.40, 0.1650736 \rangle$	$\langle 0.1550735, 0.50, 0.1550735 \rangle$	$\langle 0.1450734, 0.40, 0.1650736 \rangle$

Juror - 3:

Table 4.9: *n-CyN* values of criticism made by juror - 3

cases \ juries	jury - 1	jury - 2	jury - 3
1	$\langle 0.1850738, 0.60, 0.1150731 \rangle$	$\langle 0.1750737, 0.50, 0.1250732 \rangle$	$\langle 0.1750737, 0.50, 0.1250732 \rangle$
2	$\langle 0.1750737, 0.50, 0.1250732 \rangle$	$\langle 0.1750737, 0.50, 0.1250732 \rangle$	$\langle 0.1750737, 0.50, 0.1250732 \rangle$
3	$\langle 0.1650736, 0.50, 0.1250732 \rangle$	$\langle 0.1550735, 0.50, 0.1550735 \rangle$	$\langle 0.1650736, 0.50, 0.1250732 \rangle$
4	$\langle 0.1950739, 0.70, 0.1150731 \rangle$	$\langle 0.1950739, 0.70, 0.1150731 \rangle$	$\langle 0.1950739, 0.70, 0.1150731 \rangle$
5	$\langle 0.1450734, 0.40, 0.1650736 \rangle$	$\langle 0.1550735, 0.50, 0.1550735 \rangle$	$\langle 0.1450734, 0.40, 0.1650736 \rangle$

Juror - 4:

Table 4.10: $n-CyN$ values of criticism made by juror - 4

cases \ juries	jury - 1	jury - 2	jury - 3
1	$\langle 0.1250732, 0.30, 0.1750737 \rangle$	$\langle 0.1150731, 0.20, 0.1950739 \rangle$	$\langle 0.1550735, 0.50, 0.1550735 \rangle$
2	$\langle 0.1850738, 0.60, 0.1150731 \rangle$	$\langle 0.1150731, 0.20, 0.1950739 \rangle$	$\langle 0.1550735, 0.50, 0.1550735 \rangle$
3	$\langle 0.1450734, 0.40, 0.1650736 \rangle$	$\langle 0.1750737, 0.50, 0.1250732 \rangle$	$\langle 0.1250732, 0.30, 0.1750737 \rangle$
4	$\langle 0.1650736, 0.50, 0.1250732 \rangle$	$\langle 0.1550735, 0.50, 0.1550735 \rangle$	$\langle 0.1950739, 0.70, 0.1150731 \rangle$
5	$\langle 0.1750737, 0.50, 0.1250732 \rangle$	$\langle 0.1550735, 0.50, 0.1550735 \rangle$	$\langle 0.1650736, 0.50, 0.1250732 \rangle$

Juror - 5:

Table 4.11: $n-CyN$ values of criticism made by juror- 5

cases \ juries	jury - 1	jury - 2	jury - 3
1	$\langle 0.1950739, 0.70, 0.1150731 \rangle$	$\langle 0.1850738, 0.60, 0.1150731 \rangle$	$\langle 0.1750737, 0.50, 0.1250732 \rangle$
2	$\langle 0.1150731, 0.20, 0.1950739 \rangle$	$\langle 0.1250732, 0.30, 0.1750737 \rangle$	$\langle 0.1450734, 0.40, 0.1650736 \rangle$
3	$\langle 0.1850738, 0.60, 0.1150731 \rangle$	$\langle 0.1750737, 0.50, 0.1250732 \rangle$	$\langle 0.1650736, 0.50, 0.1250732 \rangle$
4	$\langle 0.1250732, 0.30, 0.1750737 \rangle$	$\langle 0.1550735, 0.50, 0.1550735 \rangle$	$\langle 0.1650736, 0.50, 0.1250732 \rangle$
5	$\langle 0.1750737, 0.50, 0.1250732 \rangle$	$\langle 0.1650736, 0.50, 0.1250732 \rangle$	$\langle 0.1550735, 0.50, 0.1550735 \rangle$

Juror - 1:

Table 4.12: $n-CyNE_{npy}$ criticism by juror - 1

cases	$n-CyNE_{npy}$
Case 1	0.9980532944
Case 2	0.998749975
Case 3	1
Case 4	0.9980799616
Case 5	0.9999199984

Juror - 2:

Table 4.13: $n-CyNE_{npy}$ criticism by juror - 2

cases	$n-CyNE_{npy}$
Case 1	0.998749975
Case 2	0.98624985833
Case 3	0.98666653333
Case 4	0.9985266372
Case 5	0.9998399968

Juror - 3:

Table 4.14: $n-CyNE_{npy}$ criticism by juror r - 3

cases	$n-CyNE_{npy}$
Case 1	0.9985133036
Case 2	0.998749975
Case 3	0.98666653333
Case 4	0.9980799616
Case 5	0.9998399968

Juror - 4:

Table 4.15: $n-CyNE_{npy}$ criticism by juror - 4

cases	$n-CyNE_{npy}$
Case 1	0.9977099542
Case 2	0.9976399528
Case 3	0.9989199784
Case 4	0.99269325387
Case 5	0.99291659167

Juror - 5:

Table 4.16: $n-CyNE_{npy}$ criticism by juror - 5

cases	$n-CyNE_{npy}$
Case 1	0.9982899658
Case 2	0.9976299526
Case 3	0.99226324527
Case 4	0.99274992167
Case 5	0.99291659167

Here, we can see that all the $n-CyNE_{npy}$ values of Jury - 2 are less than that of other juries. Thus evaluation done by Jury - 2 is more certain.

Hence, the ranking given in voir dire is given below as in Table 4.17

Table 4.17: Ranking based on $n-CyNE_{npy}$

Jury	Rank
Jury - 1	V
Jury - 2	I
Jury - 3	IV
Jury - 4	III
Jury - 5	II

4. Conclusions

In this paper, we have studied the concepts of $n-CyNMos$ and $n-CyNMcs$, along with their corresponding interior and closure operators within $n-CyNts$. Fundamental properties of these structures have been explored and illustrated through examples in the same setting. As a potential direction for future research, these results may be extended to n -cylindrical neutrosophic M -continuous, M -open, and M -closed mappings in $n-CyNts$. Furthermore, we apply an entropy-based measure for solving a decision-making problem related to the jury selection in voir-dire. This measure aligns well with similar approaches used for fs 's, ifs 's, and related frameworks. Hence, the proposed entropy measure is a valid tool for quantifying uncertainty in such applications.

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